

Phonological domains in Dyirbal

Anne Pycha
UC Berkeley

Primary source

Dixon, R.M.W. 1972. *The Dyirbal Language of North Queensland*. Cambridge University Press.

I. Author's definition of p-word:

- marked by an initial stressed syllable
- marked by a final inflectional ending
- has a fixed form; the 'constituents' of a word can't be permuted within a word (contrast with relatively free word order) (p. 269)

II. Notes on syllable structure

No clear criteria for syllable structure. A medial CCC cluster can be syllabified as either C.CC or CC.C (p. 274).

III. Observed Phonotactic Patterns

Roots, and hence pwords, must begin with a consonant and cannot begin with a consonant cluster. Both are minimally disyllabic.

Intra-morphemic clusters may consist of two or three consonants, subject to the following restrictions (p. 272):

- only one of *l*, *r*, ɲ , *y* can occur, it must be the initial C in cluster
- only one of *b*, *d* (apical), *d* ɲ (laminal), *g*, *w* can occur, it must be final C in cluster
- nasal + *w* prohibited
- *n* can be followed by any nasal or stop; can be preceded by *l* or *y* only, and then only when followed by non-homorganic nasal or stop
- *d* can only be preceded by *n*
- otherwise, all nasals and stops in cluster must be homorganic
- no clusters of identical segments

Inter-morphemic clusters:

- Nouns and Adjectives: a wider array of medial clusters is tolerated across morpheme boundaries than intramorphemically.
- Verbs: medial clusters across boundaries are limited to those which occur intramorphemically.

Vowels and glides are subject to the following pword constraints:

- *-iy-* can only occur when immediately followed by *-i* (i.e., **-iya-*, **-iyu-*, **-iyb-*, etc.)
- *-wi-* can occur in stressed syllable only

III. P-Rules & Processes, and the Morpho-Syntactic Information they Reference

Stress

The first syllable of every root, and hence every pword, is stressed. The first syllable of every suffix is also stressed.

The ideal pattern is for the first and all odd-numbered syllables to be stressed. To that end, the first syllable of a suffix loses its stress when immediately following a stressed syllable, or when word-final.

Thus for roots *ɔ́ínay* ‘sit’, *búybal* ‘hide’ and affixes *-mál* ~ *-mbál* ‘comitative/instrumentive’, ‘ríy’ ‘reflexive’, we get the following:

búybarí <u>u</u>	ɔ́ínayman
búybarí <u>m</u> ban	ɔ́ínaymá <u>r</u> i <u>u</u>

Insertion of -n-

-n- is inserted at certain grammatical boundaries within a word. As the following list shows, the process appears to be primarily morphologically conditioned, but within these, it may also be conditioned by certain phonological environments. Insertion takes place:

- In the dative inflection after a stressed syllable (*-ngú* after stress, *-gú* otherwise).
- Between genitive *-ɔ́u* and catalytic *-dɔ́in*: *ɔ́áliɔ́ú-dɔ́in*
- Between disyllabic stems and transitive verbalizing affix (*-mál* after disyllable, *-bál* elsewhere).
- Before the verbal stem-forming *-bál*.
- Between a *-y* stem and affixes *-gániy* and *-dɔ́ay*.
- Between an *-l* stem and reciprocal *-báriy*. This occurs ‘often’.
- Between *-ɔ́á* and nominal affix *-bila* (in Dyrbal and Giramay dialects), *-bá* (in Mamu dialect). Result is *-ɔ́ámbila*.
- Between a noun or verb marker ending in a vowel or *-y* and a following bound form: *baýingúya*
- In reduplicated forms of markers: *baýim**u**báyi*
- Between *-y* stem and verbal affix *-bila*.

-n- assimilation

An inserted *-n-* is assimilated in place to the following stop, in many but not all cases. It is more likely to assimilate before *b* than *g*.

Stress-sensitive suffix alternations

A number of suffixes alternate depending upon whether they attach to a stem in which the ‘preferred’ stress pattern prevails (that is, stress on initial syll and every odd syll after that) or not. For example:

Comitative/instrumentive: *-mál* when next but one after stressed syllable
-mbál elsewhere

núdin

núdilman (stress regularly deletes when word-final)

núdildáymban

Syllable-counting suffix alternations

The ergative suffix alternates according to the following conditions:

- *-gú* with a stem of three or more syllables, ending in a vowel
- *-ngú* with a disyllabic stem, ending in a vowel
- a homorganic stop plus *-ú* after a nasal or *-y*
- *-ú* with deletion of the stem-final consonant, in the case of a stem ending in *-l*, *-r*, or *-r*.

Coalescence

The following cases of coalescence occur:

1. Sequences of *ny* coalesce to \emptyset

gíyi-yúgul → gíyinyúgul (by *n* insertion) → gíyiúgul

gíyi = Class I demonstrative noun marker

yúgul = 'that's the one'

2. Sequences of *yn* coalesce to \emptyset

...y-nu → u (e.g. between a *-y* stem and the non-future tense *-nu*)

3. Sequences of *yd* coalesce to \emptyset

áy-da → áda

4. *y*-deletion occurs in many cases where an impossible sequence would otherwise result.

bániy-gú → bánígu

(Sequence *-iy-* is only permitted before *-i*)

5. Deletion of the second nasal in nasal-nasal clusters occurs where an impossible sequence would result, or when an infrequent cluster would result.

bálam-á → bálama

IV. Available morpheme types include

Roots

Suffixes

Non-inflecting particles and clitics that are added to the first word of a sentence